

Use of Potassium Bromate : Oxidation of Benzaldehyde

AMALENDU BANERJEE, (Mrs.) SANTA BANERJEE^a and HARAPRASAD SAMADDAR^b

Teachers Fellow (U.G.C.), Chemistry Department, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 13 November 1978, accepted 6 October 1979

Oxidation of benzaldehyde under various conditions using potassium bromate as the oxidising agent has been discussed.

POTASSIUM bromate is a powerful oxidising agent which is cheap, easily available and offers least possible trouble compared to other oxidising agents¹ during the work up of the reaction product. Literature survey reveals that some works on kinetic study²⁻⁸ have been done with this reagent and we are not aware of its previous use in oxidising aldehydes and similar organic compounds. Easily oxidisable benzaldehyde had been chosen as the pilot compound for the study of the oxidation which reacted with potassium bromate in distilled acetic acid medium at elevated temperature within ten minutes to furnish benzoic acid in excellent yield. It had also been observed that one mole of the reagent consumed three moles of benzaldehyde under this condition. But the oxidation with the reagent in (4*N*) sulphuric acid medium produced a mixture of products containing (a) benzoic acid and (b) *m*-bromobenzoic acid. The separation of the mixture of acidic products (a) and (b) mentioned above presented lots of difficulties. The recrystallisations from various solvents and chromatographic separation of the ethyl ester on neutral alumina were not operative as well as thin layer chromatographic method on silicagel was not successful. Distillation of the esters of the acid mixtures under reduced pressure followed by the hydrolysis of each fraction made it possible to separate the acid mixtures into its components. Oxidation with this reagent was unsuccessful in neutral or alkaline medium. However, benzaldehyde underwent slow aerial oxidation when heated for longer period under experimental condition without the use of potassium bromate. It was noticed that when potassium bromate was heated in (4*N*) sulphuric acid, bromine and oxygen were liberated which were not found when (0.5*N*) sulphuric acid was used. A little amount of oxygen and bromine were liberated if distilled glacial acetic acid was used. It had been observed that the liberated bromine had

little effect in the oxidation reaction though large excess of elemental bromine oxidised benzaldehyde in approximately 50%, when conducted either in distilled glacial acetic acid or in dilute (1 : 1) acetic acid under the present experimental conditions. Mercuric acetate did not oxidise benzaldehyde under similar experimental condition.

Excellent results have been obtained by using potassium bromate under acidic condition during oxidation of various carbonyl compounds, alcohols and other classes of organic compounds which will be reported in future communications.

Experimental

A. R. acetic acid was heated under reflux with excess of potassium dichromate for six hours and distilled just before use. Pure potassium bromate, sulphuric acid and distilled water were used whenever needed.

1. (a) Oxidation of Benzaldehyde with Potassium Bromate in (4*N*) Sulphuric Acid :

A mixture of benzaldehyde (3.8 g), potassium bromate (2.0 g) and sulphuric acid (4*N*; 10 ml) was heated under reflux for thirty minutes. Bromine was evolved and potassium bromate was found to be completely decomposed. Again potassium bromate (1.0 g) was added to the reaction mixture and heating was continued for further thirty minutes. The cold reaction mixture was treated with ether and the ethereal layer was extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The alkaline extract was acidified (congo-red) with dilute sulphuric acid and the

^aChemistry Department, Dinabandhu Andrews College, Garia, 24-Parganas, West Bengal.

^bChemistry Department, Ramakrishna Mission Residential College, Narendrapur, 24-Parganas, West Bengal.

precipitated material was filtered and air-dried, the crude material (3.2 g; m. p. 131-135°) was recrystallised from hot water after treatment with activated charcoal to furnish colourless crystals (0.5 g. m. p. 141-142°), which responded to the Beilstein test and Lassaigne's sodium fusion test for the presence of bromine. This material further crystallized from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether (60-80°) to yield a colourless acidic material (0.3 g), m. p. 154-155°, m. m. p. of which remained undepressed with authentic *m*-bromobenzoic acid (m. p. 155°); neutral equivalent of the compound was found to be 198 ± 5 . The I.R. spectra of this sample and the authentic *m*-bromobenzoic acid were identical in all respects: $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$, 1680, 1590, 1560, 1455, 1440, 998, 939, 900, 831, 816, 745, 700, 668 and 548 cm^{-1} . The aqueous mother liquor from the initial crystallisation was treated with dilute sulphuric acid and sodium chloride until saturated, and extracted with ether. On drying and removal of the solvent a residue (0.6 g), m. p. 79-83° was obtained which showed the presence of bromine. This was supposed to be a mixture of benzoic and *m*-bromobenzoic acids as evident from the fact that equal amount of these authentic acids when mixed together melted at 80-95°.

The neutral part contained in the initial ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed from steambath to yield the unreacted benzaldehyde (1.3 g), identified through its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative (m. p. 235° d).

(b) The above experiment was repeated by heating under reflux a mixture of benzaldehyde (20.0 g) and a thirty millilitre of a solution of potassium bromate [Prepared from potassium bromate (12.0 g), water (100 ml) and sulphuric acid (4*N*; 50 ml)]. After ten minutes interval another portion of thirty millilitre of potassium bromate solution was added and the reaction mixture was again heated under reflux for five minutes. This step was repeated until the addition was completed and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for a total period of one hour. It was observed that after each addition bromine was evolved and after one hour of heating the reaction mixture became transparent and almost colourless. This was then cooled to room temperature and the precipitated material was filtered and air-dried. The crude acid, thus obtained, was then dried by repeated addition and distillation of dry benzene to it and a residue (27.5 g) was obtained. The increase in weight of this dried crude material indicated 34% production of bromobenzoic acid.

The ethyl ester of this material (27.5 g) was prepared by dissolving in bidistilled ethyl alcohol (120 ml) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux on steambath for fourteen hours. The reaction mixture was worked up in the usual way to furnish the crude

ester (24.0 g), b.p. 195-201°, responding strongly to the Beilstein test for halogen.

The ester (6.0 g) was hydrolysed by heating under reflux with an ethanolic solution of potassium hydroxide (3.2 g) containing a few drops of distilled water, for two hours on steambath. The acidic material was isolated in the usual way when a colourless crystalline material (5.0 g) m. p. 69-74° was obtained, which on repeated crystallisation furnished pure benzoic acid in approximately 50% yield.

2. Oxidation of Benzaldehyde with Potassium Bromate in Distilled Glacial Acetic Acid :

To a mixture of benzaldehyde (10.5 g) and potassium bromate (12.0 g), acetic acid (50 ml) was added and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for ten minutes, then formic acid was added dropwise to decompose the liberated bromine. This was cooled and then poured into ice-water (200 ml). The colourless crystalline solid, thus separated, was extracted with chloroform (3×50 ml). The organic extract was washed with water and extracted with excess of saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with (4*N*), sulphuric acid and the colourless crystalline solid, thus separated, was extracted with ether (3×100 ml). The organic extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a colourless crystalline residue (11.0 g), m. p. 121°, was obtained. A small portion of the acid was recrystallised from hot water when characteristic flaky crystals of benzoic acid, m.p. 122°, was obtained which remained undepressed on admixture with authentic benzoic acid. When this experiment was repeated several times by heating under reflux for two, five and fifteen minutes, the yields of the benzoic acid were 60.9%, 78.3% and 97% respectively.

3. Oxidation of Benzaldehyde with Varying Amounts of Potassium Bromate :

In separate experiments a mixture of benzaldehyde (6.35 g; 0.06 *M*), acetic acid (10 ml) and varying amounts of potassium bromate 0.35 g (0.002 *M*); 0.70 g (0.004 *M*); 1.35 g (0.008 *M*); 2.60 g (0.012 *M*) and 2.70 g (0.016 *M*) were heated under reflux for ten minutes in each experiment. The reaction mixture was worked up by the method described before to furnish pure benzoic acid, m.p. 122°, in quantitative yield in each case. The unreacted benzaldehyde was isolated in each case in the usual way (5.3 g, 4.5 g, 3.3 g, 2.0 g, and 0.8 g respectively) and characterised through 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative, m. p. 235° d).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. N. Das, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur

University, Calcutta-700032, for providing laboratory facilities. The award of the Teacher Fellowship to one of us (H. S.) by the University Grants Commission is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. L. F. FIESER and M. FIESER in "Reagents for Organic Synthesis", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, London, Sydney, Vol. 1-6.
2. L. FARKAS and O. SCHACHATER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2827.
3. F. J. R. HIRD and J. R. YATES, *J. Sci. Food Agr.*, 1961, **12**, 89-95.
4. I. V. KOLOZOV and A. E. KUZ'MINA (U.S.S.R.) *Izv. Timiryazev Sel'skokhoz Akad.*, 1969, (1), 203-7 (Russ.).
5. R. NATARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, **57**, 5021.
6. R. NATARAJAN and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Tetrahedron*, 1974, **30**, 2785.
7. VIJAYALAXMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 612.
8. VIJAYALAXMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 567.